

Investigation into the analysis method of the Rubber Anti-oxidant RD by HPLC gradient elution

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Manuscript received online 09 June 2012, revised 08 January 2013, accepted 20 July 2013

Abstract : RD (2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline polymer (C₁₂H₁₅N)_n, n = 2~4, TMDQP) the higher the polymer content, the better the quality, but in the national standards, lack of assay methods, and lack of communication between the business and technology of mutual confidence, and therefore there is no uniform way to explore a simple and fast, and reliable detection method is necessary, will promote the RD industry. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) more quickly and accurately, this study used HPLC, using gradient elution, a determination of three kinds of polymer content, saving a lot of time, accurate data. Shimadzu C₁₈ column and 150 mm length was used and the mobile phase was water and methanol, mobile phase flow rate was 1.0 mL min⁻¹, wavelength was UV at 254 nm and the sample volume was 20 μL. Gradient conditions methanol : 65%, 12.5%/min; 65-75%, 12.5%/min; 75-85%, 12.5%/min; 85-90%, 12.5%/min; 90-95%, 12.5%/min; 95% remain 10 min; 95-100%, 12.5%/min; 100% remain 10 min.

Keywords : RD (2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline polymer (C₁₂H₁₅N)_n, n = 2~4, TMDQP), content, HPLC

Introduction

Rubber Anti-oxidant RD^{1,2} (polymerized-2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline resin. Molecular formula (C₁₂H₁₅N)_n, n = 2-4, TMDQP) is a ketone amine anti-oxidant. Rubber Antioxidant RD is a kind of amber to brown flake or powder. It is well known that RD polymer is an excellent antioxidant for rubber. It has performed excellently on the protection of oxidation of rubber which is caused by thermal oxidative aging and catalytic oxidation by metal ions. RD is mainly used for natural rubber and chloroprene rubber etc. It has excellent effects on the ageing caused by heating and oxygen, and it has strongly restrained impact on the metallic catalysis and oxidation, it is suitable for natural, buna-s, buna-N and chloroprene rubbers. Rubber Antioxidant RD has a longer-time remaining of protective effect, because it has a higher molecular weight and has little diffusive loss. So it is suitable for the rubber products used in the tropical area.

Anti-degradants for rubber comprising of a mixture consisting essentially of 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquino-

line³⁻⁸ monomer, dimer thereof and more highly polymerized products than the dimer the contents of the quinoline dimer being less than 20 wt% and 30 wt% or even more, respectively. The anti-degradants for rubber are very useful for preventing both heat aging and flex cracking of rubber. Content of Rubber Anti-oxidant RD for dimer, trimer and tetramer have a great impact on their quality, but now there are lacking standards for measurement methods. Fast and accurate measurements are in urgent need.

In the research, content of RD was determined by Highly effective liquid phase chromatography (HPLC). Through using the gradient elution method, the content of dimer, trimer and tetramer were determined and time was saved at the same time. Gradient elution can help improve separating degree, shorten the separation time, reduce the minimum testing quantity and improve the separation accuracy.

Experimental

Materials and equipment :

HPLC grade methanol and acetonitrile were purchased

from fisher and RD sample made by oneself. Hitachi L-2000 HPLC inclusion auto-sampler L-2200, organizer, UV-Vis detector L-2420 (200–900 nm) and Pump L-2130. Chromatographic column Shimadzu C₁₈ (4.6 mm × 150 mm/5 μm). Shimadzu UV 2200, Satorious electronic balance B204-N (Max 210 g; d = 0.1 mg). Ultrasound cleaner etc.

UV detection wavelength selection :

HPLC, wavelength selection is determined in accordance with the test substance is the maximum absorption wavelength. Typically, the detector high performance liquid chromatography with UV detection, the HPLC wavelength selection and UV wavelength selection are to select the maximum absorption wavelength, this will ensure the sensitivity and the highest response value.

RD in methanol for all wavelengths of UV (190~400 nm) energy scan shown in the Fig. 1.

Based on Fig. 1 in the energy absorption peak around 250 nm, and 250 nm before and after the peak did not interfere with others, measured wavelength is 254 nm. So we choose RD test wavelength UV 254 nm.

The content analysis process of RD sample :

In the first place, RD in the ground into fine powder in a mortar, take the RD sample precision 0.0015 g. In the second, RD put into 5 ml volumetric flask, add half of the methanol solvent, ultrasonic 10 min, cooled to room temperature, constant volume, ultrasonic 10 min. Micro-porous membrane with 0.25 μm filter, discard to filtrate to the beginning, the filtrate added to the vial, by HPLC detection. The whole analysis process shown in the Fig. 2.

The mobile phase selection :

Reversed phase chromatography mobile phase usually with water as a basic solvent, miscible with water,

Fig. 1. UV energy scan.

Fig. 2. The content analysis process of RD sample.

then add a certain amount of polar modifier, such as methanol, acetonitrile, tetrahydrofuran, and so on. The nature and proportion of the polar modifier on solute retention and separation selectivity have a significant effect. Under normal circumstances, the methanol-water system has been able to meet the separation requirements of the majority of samples, and the mobile phase viscosity, low prices, reversed phase chromatography the most commonly used mobile phase.

In general, methanol-water system has been able to meet the requirements of the separation of most samples, and the mobile phase viscosity, low price, is the most commonly used reversed-phase HPLC mobile phase. RD solubility in water because of the smaller, more organic solvents in the solubility increases. Taking into account the volatile reagents, toxicity and economic factors, the trial use of methanol-water as mobile phase.

Selection gradient of solvent :

For the composition of complex samples, using a chromatographic system, it is difficult to get good separation. Alternatively separated too long, or poor separation. In the shortest possible time in order to get good separation, usually in liquid chromatography using gradient elution to achieve their goals.

The main purpose of gradient elution is to move strongly retained components of the mixture faster, but having the least retained component well resolved. Starting with the low content of the organic component in the eluent we allow the least retained components to be separated. Strongly retained components will sit on the adsorbent surface on the top of the column, or will move very slowly.

When we start to increase an amount of organic component in the eluent (methanol) then strongly retained components will move faster and faster, because of the steady increase of the competition for the adsorption sites. Gradient elution also increased quasi-efficiency of the column. In the isocratic elution, the longer a component is retained, the wider its peak. In gradient elution, especially with the smooth gradient shape without a flat region, the tail of the peak is always under the influence of the stronger mobile phase when compared to the peak front. Thus, molecules on the tail of the chromatographic zone (peak) will move faster. This will tend to compress zone and narrow the resultant peak. Performance of the

gradient elution is strongly dependent on the instrumentation. Two main points the chromatographer needs to know about his instrument : How large the volume between the component mixing point and column inlet.

For the low-pressure gradient systems this volume usually correspond to the pump volume, and about 2–3 ml. How well does the system mix eluent components. If the system does not mix components well then it will supply for the certain time one component then another and so on. Chromatographic performance of such system will be very low especially for the least retained components.

The process of analysis of RD is shown in Fig. 2.

In the first place, choose a superior performance of the C₁₈ or C₈ bonded phase as the initial method development. The bond corresponding to the acidic, alkaline and neutral compounds can provide good peak shape and retention.

Second, optimization of mobile phase composition of organic phase to change its selectivity. Due to RD can be dissolved in ethanol, methanol and acetone which selection gradient of methanol. Because the 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline is soluble in methanol of 50 v/v% to 100 v/v%. Gradient selection in the Table 1.

Table 1. Optimizing of gradient of mobile phase

$\frac{C}{T}$	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80
1	45	50	55	60	65	70	80	90	100
2	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	90	100
3	55	60	65	70	75	80	90	95	100
4	60	65	70	75	80	85	95	100	100
5	65	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100
6	65	65	75	80	85	90	95	100	100
7	65	65	75	85	85	90	95	100	100
8	65	65	75	85	90	95	95	100	100
9	65	65	75	85	90	90	95	95	100
10	65	65	75	85	90	90	100	100	100
11	65	65	75	85	95	100	100	100	100
12	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100	100
13	65	70	75	80	85	90	90	95	100
14	65	70	75	85	95	100	100	100	100
15	65	70	80	90	95	100	100	100	100

(T = time, C = concentration of methanol %).

Obtained HPLC chromatograms after optimization is to optimize the conditions to get the Table 2 and standard HPLC chromatogram shown in Fig. 3.

Table 2. Gradient of mobile phase

Time (min)	Methanol (%)	Water (%)
0	65	35
10	65	35
20	75	25
30	85	15
40	90	10
50	95	5
60	95	5
70	100	0
80	100	0

place, RD in the ground into fine powder in a mortar, take the RD sample precision 0.0100 g. In the second RD put into 10 ml volumetric flask, add half of the methanol solvent, ultrasonic 10 min, cooled to the room temperature, constant volume, ultrasound 10 min. Micro-porous membrane with 0.25 μm filter, discard to filtrate to the beginning, the filtrate added to the vial, by HPLC detection. Mobile flow rate is 1 mL/min, wavelength UV at 254 nm, injection volume 20 μL . Tested 10 samples of RD were obtained with the concentration and HPLC chromatograms shown in the Table 3 and the Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Standard HPLC chromatogram of RD sample : (A) dimer, (B) trimer, (C) tetramer.

In terms of the gradient of mobile (Table 2) and the content analysis process of RD (Fig. 2), which analysis of RD made myself, results shown in Table 3. In the first

Discussion

Injection volume of research :

Weighed with a precision balance RD sample 0.0015 g, dissolved in 5 ml volumetric flask, ultrasound 10 min, constant volume. With a micro-porous membrane filter,

Table 3. Content of Rubber Anti-oxidant RD

No.	Dimer (%)	Trimer (%)	Tetramer (%)	Total (%)	Mean	RSD
1	24.592	15.117	5.497	45.206		
2	25.337	14.861	5.592	45.790		
3	28.749	15.568	5.229	49.546		
4	26.908	15.417	5.846	48.171		
5	25.949	15.830	6.494	48.273	45.841	0.04844
6	24.804	14.981	6.019	45.804		
7	25.819	10.667	5.726	42.212		
8	23.899	14.864	5.933	44.696		
9	23.725	15.020	5.661	44.406		
10	22.914	16.028	5.360	44.302		

Fig. 4. HPLC chromatograms of the samples of RD.

the initial filtrate was discarded, leaving the filtrate, respectively, the volume of the sampler 5 μL , 10 μL , 15 μL , 20 μL . From the peak of the situation, the injection volume of 20 μL , the better.

Temperature of column selection :

Temperature is an important factor of HPLC performance. Because of the elevated temperature, viscosity of the mobile phase decrease, backpressure over the column reduced, the speed of mobile phase can be improved, and shorten the analytical time and adjust the selectivity. At the same time, under the higher temperature, the use of organic solvent can be decreased. Elevated the analytical temperature is an efficient and economic method for high performance chromatography.

Experiment, we found that in methanol/water = 60/40 balance, fall is relatively high at room temperature about 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ when the pump pressure of 13.9 MPa, and in early winter temperature around 16 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the pump pressure 15.8 MPa. And the temperature is low, the dimer of the RD peak of parasitic peaks, but the determination is not affected.

The method of content analysis :

Content analysis of the RD by the method of area normalization. Area normalization method style is in the column, all do a measure of the peak area, according to the normalization method of calculation, and from the content components to be tested.

Percentage content = (for the compositions of the peak area for the compositions $\times$ relative calibration factor)/(sample of all kinds of material peak area $\times$ amount of the relative calibration factor).

Simple calculation, and can be used for routine analysis. It requires all of the components in the sample that peak. His advantage : into the sample weight and operat-

ing conditions on the determination results basically no influence.

Gradient elution should pay attention to each solvent solubility, the solvent, the purity of higher requirements on reproducibility. Pay attention to the system when the pressure gradient change, prevent beyond the limit, after the gradient, with initial mobile phase flush, make their balance for a period of time (regeneration), make the system returns to its original state (gradient cycle). Low voltage gradient to pay attention to take off the gas, and the mixed easy to have a bubble, prone to ghost peak, should make blank test. Gradient choose as far as possible when a few phase to phase change between small, otherwise not easy to balance gradient itself should be used for mobile phase composition change not sensitive selective detector (such as ultraviolet absorption detector or fluorescence detector), and not the use of the mobile phase composition change sensitive universal detector (such as poor and refractive index detector).

Acknowledgement

Thanks for Hankook Tyre Co., Ltd., Jiaying Zhejiang and Huaguang Chemical Ltd. for the research support.

References

1. Cyril A. Migdal and Ronald D. Abbott, US Patent, 6,726,855 B1 (2004).
2. Takashi Kojima and Ryozo Ishimoto, US Patent, 4,326,062 (1982).
3. Knoevenagel Jaegar, *Ber Dtsch ChemGes.*, 1921, **54**, 1723.
4. I. W. Elliott and P. Yates, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1287.
5. D. Craig and E. Gregg, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2252.
6. W. Johson and B. Buell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4517.
7. J. P. Brown, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, **9**, 233.
8. I. S. Akhrem, I. M. Churilova, A. V. Orlinkov, L. V. Afanas'eva, S. V. Vitt and P. V. Petrovskii, *Russian Chemical Bulletin*, 1998, 47(5).

